

Otkir Hoshimov's " Lifes passed in a dream"

Odambaeva Yulduzxon Ahmad qizi

The student of Foreign language and literature department

Kamilova Rozakhon Dilshod qizi

The teacher of Foreign language and literature department

Urgench State Pedagogical Institute

Khorezm, Uzbekistan

Abstract: Otkir Hoshimov is one of the great uzbek writers whose works are still the favourite ones for every booklover. His works are like water for the soul. While reading Hoshimov's novels a reader imagines oneself as the main character. His works open a new world for every reader. Regardless of the topic of his novel and story, he awakens a deep feeling in the soul of every reader.

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Otkir Hoshimov is one of the writers who made a great contribution to Uzbek literature of the twentieth century. His works such as "Between Two Doors", "Works of the World", and "Spring will not return" are in the hearts of readers. One such work is the novel "Lifetimes spent in a dream". The work was written in 1991-1992. The work has a unique structure. It contains clips from Rustam's diary and information from investigative documents. The story begins with the image of autumn and ends with the same image: Autumn is like a patient on his deathbed. Sick hazans groan under his feet... Realizing that all his efforts have been wasted, he looks at the world sadly. A white mist like a shroud covers the earth. From the white darkness, the uncharacteristic squawk of crows is heard." The likeness of autumn to a patient lying on the death bed, the moaning of hazans, the white fog covering the earth and the sky like a shroud, the careless crowing of crows indicate that there are some unconscious situations in the work. One of the main characters of the play, Rustam, quits his studies and joins the army. From the army, he is sent to Afghanistan, where the war is going on. He fought not for his country and people, but for the political interests of the Soviet government, which consisted of occupation. He witnessed how young men like him, like Timur, Hayriddin, died for nothing in the territory of Afghanistan, and how Afghans suffered greatly from the war. As a result of the war, he fell ill. Rustam could not get rid of the memories of

the Afghan war. ... Even though he married Shahnoza, the girl he loved, and even though they loved each other very much, they could not be happy. The main reason for these misfortunes was the negative impact of the war. After returning home, witnessing injustices and injustices, feeling guilty for his wife's misfortune, led to his tragic death.

Commissioner Soat Ganiyev arouses hatred in the heart of every reader. He followed in his father's footsteps and became a Soviet commissar. This man, who has caused many people (Mahalladoshi Husan, Tolagan) to be unjustly punished since his youth, who defiled a woman, will not regret it even in his old age. He does not regret his past life. does not change the world view. The commissioner is a symbol of the 70-year reign of oppression. He is not ordinary, he is a very dangerous manqurt.

Aunt Qurbanoy does not know what she has spent her life on, even if her health deteriorates and she is unable to work, she does not stop her daily chores. Doctors are busy with their daily worries, even if they don't know what they know. This woman's life was as meaningless and miserable as in a dream. Why is the work called Lifetimes in the Dream?

In the process of reading the work, I witnessed that it reflected the sad nightmare of the life of the characters, that is, the darkness of life. Rustam's participation in the Afghan war and the details of the war, the successive tragic deaths of people who managed to be close to him, the death of Rustam, who could not achieve a happy life due to the disease he acquired in the war, and the life of Shahnaza, who has not yet felt what happiness is.

The life of aunt Kurbanoi, who lived only in sorrow throughout her life. The life of a commissar who believes that what he does is right, that his heinous deeds are the most righteous way. It is because of this commissioner that the life of a sincere, honest and pure teacher whose life ended tragically.

The work clearly reflects the unjust injustices inflicted on people during the period of repression.

In the mid-1980s, under the guise of combating and eliminating bribery under the guise of "cotton work" and "Uzbek work", the center carried out "political cleansing" in Uzbekistan. such "cleaning works" were carried out every ten years during the era of the Rolar period. In the mid-80s, thousands of Uzbeks were imprisoned in the "Uzbeks' case" led by H. Gdlyan and I. Ivanov from Moscow. Thousands of specialists from the center were transferred to Uzbekistan. All possibilities were used to keep the people in slavery. It should be noted that the

former alliance was fake from the beginning. Republics were forced to join him. The problems accumulated during the nearly seventy-year rule of the Soviet system began to emerge in the eighties. It is no longer possible to control the union by force. When Mikhail Gorbachev came to the top of the government, he began to implement the policy of "Reconstruction" to solve the accumulated problems. Repressions during Stalin's time covered the entire union, but during the period of reconstruction, the cloud of repressions only discredited one nation. False fictions such as "Cotton case" and "Uzbeks case" were invented. The aim was to eliminate problems such as headship, corruption, and corruption, which have escalated in the Union, on the example of Uzbekistan. The leaders of the Communist Party set themselves the goal of discrediting Uzbekistan and intimidating other republics. In 1985, the next plenum of the Communist Party analyzed the situation in the country and issued instructions on the need to renew the Soviet society.

As a result, "Personnel landing" was sent to Uzbekistan. A group of investigators led by Gdlyan and Ivanov, employees of the USSR Prosecutor's Office, rolled up their sleeves and got to work. The investigators accused the Uzbek people of fraud, bribery, plagiarism, hooliganism, etc.

As a result of the "Cotton Affair", about twenty-five thousand citizens of our republic were tortured and imprisoned without trial. The repressions that have been carried out continuously for years, the tense situation that has arisen in the former union and our republic, the trampling of national customs and traditions, and even the inability to follow a close relative to his last destination when he dies, and other situations open people's eyes. started A mood of protest began to appear among the people. O'tkir Hashimov, who saw these events with his own eyes and was moved, turned these events into a work of art. The novel is written with intense pain, in which we see a creator whose thoughts have deepened and social pains have matured. A deep penetration into the life of society, a subtle description of the psyche of people is clearly visible in "Lives passed in a dream" compared to other novels of the writer.

. Rasulov explains that the effect of independence is felt in the spirit and content of the work as follows: O'Hoshimov did not limit himself in illuminating the character of people in "Dream of Lives". As in the time of the Shura, it is impossible to reflect this, there is no longer the pressure of unwritten laws, which say that a person should be illuminated mainly in his social essence." If this work had been written during the Shura era, it would not have been published. Because people like Saat Ganiyevich, who devoted his whole life to serving the state of the Soviets, turned

the children of our nation into "alien elements" with his own hands, rose to the top during the autocratic regime. Saat Ganievich is not just an image. The writer also reflected the social system of the Soviet era in his image. The concept of religion and nation is completely foreign to him. He is a Chekist who is suspicious of his wife and child. The Mustabid regime raised such people.

The novel portrays real-life scenes by gathering Rustam, his beloved wife Shakhnoza, and Rustam's parents into the main plot line. The play begins with the death of Rustam. During the development of events, the writer reveals the essence of the system that caused the tragedy of the Rustams while determining the details of the main character's death. It skillfully shows that the human child has no dignity and that their fate is decided in the hands of the commissars who created the system. It seems illogical for a noble and brave young man like Rustam to commit suicide in the prime of his youth. But if you think carefully, the Afghan war, its thousands of innocent victims, and the repressions imposed on the people under the pretext of "Uzbek affairs" are illogical. Rustam is a victim of this irrationality. In one of his interviews, the writer says about this: "Those were the times when the time of the Shura came to an end. On the one hand, there is an Afghan war. On the other hand, under the pretext of "Uzbek affairs", our people are playing with the sword of repression. "Iron coffins" of our young soldiers arrive one day from Afghanistan and one day from inside the country. Just like a nightmare..."

The writer said that when a number of chapters from the novel "Late Lives in a Dream" were being published in English in the foreign magazine "Ikarus", he asked, "What do you like about him?" I asked. "There is no politics in it, i.e. there is no saying that this is communist, this is fascist, this is red, this is white, this is friend, this is enemy. In this work, there are three things: war, man, and death," the publishers answered. Indeed, it is about war and its harmful effects on ordinary people.

Said Ahmed gives the following assessment to the work "Lives passed in a dream". "A novel cannot be read without apathy, it shakes the reader. He curses from the bottom of his heart to the crazy warmongers who started a bloody war that brought nothing but death upon the people.

O'tkir Hoshimov, one of the outstanding creators of Uzbek prose of the 20th century, brought the word to the level of art, sought novelty and artistic excellence from its every layer, and considered this excellence as the core of creativity. is a knowledgeable writer. The study of literary works, the unique style and artistic skills of the writer, the plot of the work, the system of images, the writer's style, and skills

are the main tasks of our graduation-qualification work. was studied. O‘tkir Hashimov's novel, "Dreams of the past" in a wider and more detailed way, in the middle of the book, the "cotton issue" that defames the Uzbek people, and the "Uzbek issue" is the fire that burned the land. The fact that Gdlyans from the center made full use of the "unlimited right" given to them and made thousands of families happy, allows one to get a broad idea of the horrors and tragedies of the Afghan war.

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